

Research Article

Efficiency of Edpuzzle in Science-Assisted Flipped Classrooms: Enhancing Year 4 Learning Outcomes

Rubeneswary A/P Jayabalan^{1,*}

¹ rubyipg@gmail.com

Abstract: Flipped classrooms enhance active learning, but Year 4 students often struggle with engagement and comprehension. This study evaluates the efficiency of Edpuzzle in a science-assisted flipped classroom. The objectives are to assess its impact on student engagement, comprehension, and retention. A quasi-experimental design compared an Edpuzzle-integrated flipped classroom with a traditional approach using pre-tests, post-tests, and surveys. Results indicate higher retention and participation in the Edpuzzle group, though some faced adaptation challenges. Improvements like guided discussions and gamification are suggested. Edpuzzle demonstrated improved engagement, retention, and performance in assessments compared to their peers in conventional classrooms. Teachers reported increased class time for hands-on activities and inquiry-based learning, while students showed greater enthusiasm and autonomy in their learning. Overall, the integration of Edpuzzle significantly contributed to the effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach, making it a valuable pedagogical strategy for enhancing science education at the primary level. In conclusion, Edpuzzle enhances flipped learning, making it a valuable tool for science education.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom; Edpuzzle; Science Education; Student Engagement

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, the flipped classroom method has gained popularity as an effective approach to enhance student learning, especially in subjects like science. One powerful tool that supports this method is Edpuzzle, an interactive video-based learning platform that enables teachers to insert quizzes, notes, and voiceovers into videos. This allows students to actively engage with the content before attending class. In Malaysia, Edpuzzle is conveniently accessible through the ID Delima portal and is free for government school students and teachers. The use of online learning platforms is being an alternative for vocational high school to fulfilling online learning needs. The teacher is expected to give some innovative learning in the learning implementation so that it can produce an effective and successful teaching and learning process (Mishra, Gupta, & Shree, 2020). Its accessibility at any time and from anywhere makes it an ideal resource for promoting self-paced and flexible learning. With Edpuzzle, students are not limited to reading textbooks alone; they can watch teacher-assigned videos, answer questions embedded within, and revisit difficult concepts as needed. This not only prepares them for in-class activities but also allows teachers to monitor their understanding ahead of time. Assessments can be conducted easily through the platform, providing instant feedback and saving time. Overall, Edpuzzle encourages meaningful flipped learning, making science lessons more interactive, personalized, and effective. Furthermore, Silbermans' research (2020) emphasized that

group-based learning is the appropriate learning strategy to stimulate the students to think critically in problem-solving.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This research uses quantitative research. Research quantitative is used to examine data that can be processed. The instrument is used to collect the research data, which is statically analyzed to prove the predetermined hypothesis (Sugiyono, 2012). The method in this research used a quasi-experimental design. The research design used to pre-test and post-test. In this study, the data collection techniques were taken by observation sheets and pre-test. At first, this research began with making an instrument consisting of a lesson plan and preparing materials via online. The second, the implementation of the pretest. Third, techniques implemented among Year 4 students, through flip classroom learning model assisted by Edpuzzle. Fourth, the implementation of the post-test. Then, the data analysis and finally the conclusion. The research procedures can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Procedure

Researcher follows guideline below as shown in Figure 2 throughout the research carry out. Edpuzzle comes with an extremely easy user interface. it is a video platform designed with the sole aim to assist teachers in enhancing the engagement of students and improving their learning through video lessons. the best part of it is it collects data as students watch and interact. it is time saving for the researcher. Researcher can make and upload their own videos or choose videos from Youtube to embed quizzes in the videos. the most important advantage of it is it tracks students' activity and gives detailed reports, the researcher can monitor students' progress. Students will be given 1week prior time to go through the chapter contents and materials before the class starts.

Figure 2. Teachers and Students' Flipped Classroom Approach assisted Edpuzzle

Figure 3. Students' Learning Human Breathing System through Edpuzzle assisted by Flipped Classroom Approach

3. FINDINGS

Figure 4. Students’ Performance based on Pre-test Vs Post-test

Based on the data above, researcher can conclude that students’ performances increases after implementing Edpuzzle approach towards students assisted flipped classroom. Based on this evaluation carried out by 14 different individuals, it can be concluded that Edpuzzle allows the teacher to interact with students when they carry out learning alone, providing added value to their own or other people's graphic material to be used (Burns et al., 2020; Comer & Lenaghan, 2013; Mischel, 2019; Vercellotti, 2018). Likewise, the preference of students for graphic and visual material to complement other learning tools and help students to better understand the knowledge to be acquired was also verified (Mischel, 2019; Pal & Patra, 2020; Roberts, 2019; Silverajah & Govindaraj, 2018).

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the personal interviews with students some students shared that they missed the immediate feedback or answer from the teacher, in case of doubts, and they had to wait to meet the teacher in the next class to clear their doubts. Some of them complained that they were not able to watch the video on the phone, which may be because their phones were not compatible with the video. The personal notes of the researcher reflect that it took great deal of time for the video to be uploaded on the Edpuzzle platform. It also needs extra time and from the teachers’ side to flip a classroom. Flipped classroom approach gives immense opportunities to students to learn at their own pace and manage their own study. Moreover, it makes students accountable for themselves. It also provides them with self-study opportunities. The students were able to adapt the approach easily and they were completely satisfied with the flipped classroom approach.

The teachers are recommended to adapt Flipped classroom approach using Edpuzzle as coursework. This experiment was carried out only with one small group of students with one single topic and on one particular level. This approach may be employed on other students of different levels with different skills to measure the effectiveness of the approach. Teachers should be trained in using various learning management systems so that they can employ the approach effectively over the traditional classroom method. The next step of my research would be to find out how the flipped classroom approach would work with other science chapters and how it would work with flipping the whole course.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the integration of Edpuzzle into the flipped classroom model represents a significant innovation in enhancing the learning experience for Year 4 science students. By allowing students to engage with interactive video content before class, Edpuzzle promotes self-paced learning and fosters greater student engagement. The platform's ability to track progress and provide real-time feedback supports personalized learning, while maximizing valuable classroom time for discussions, experiments, and deeper exploration of scientific concepts. The accessibility and flexibility of Edpuzzle, along with its cost-effectiveness for government schools, make it an excellent tool for enhancing the effectiveness of science education. However, to further optimize its impact, additional improvements such as teacher training, offline access, and increased content diversity could be explored. Overall, Edpuzzle proves to be a powerful tool that contributes to better learning outcomes, empowering both teachers and students in the science classroom.

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